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TRANSLATION AS A WAY OF PERCEIVING A FOREIGN CULTURE**Samira Hasanova¹, Asst. Prof. Ulviyya Nasirova², Kamala Akberova³**¹Odlar Yurdu University, Department of Languages, Azerbaijan,

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Abstract

This article discusses the main problems of translation and the importance of foreign culture of the given language. Translation is a literal transfer of information into a foreign language and a cultural rethinking of all the facts that come from two participants in communication when interacting with a translation specialist. A translator should not ignore the semantic differences between languages when working on a translation - this applies to both a live dialogue in an informal setting and professional joint work on a project. Component analysis is aimed at a deep understanding of the meaning of the content of a text or oral message and its competent interpretation, accessible for understanding in the target language. In this case, the cultural features of the language are erased, and only the informative content of the original message comes to the fore. In translation work, it is important to take into account the correct interpretation of not only specific words and phrases, but also the content of each sentence as a whole in the context of the general meaning of the material. A linguist must study the cultural nuances of the target language, understand the specifics of working with a specific audience and clearly define the purpose of the information presented in written or oral form. It is important to take into account that there is always a difference in the semantic meaning of various cultural terms, and a competent translator in most cases can only approximately interpret what is said in another language, avoiding gross errors, inaccuracies and interpretation of concepts in the opposite meaning.

Key words: translation, cultural nuances, foreign language, interpretation, meaning**1.INTRODUCTION**

Language is a product of society and the crystallization of human history and culture. It embodies the characteristics of social consciousness, history and culture, customs and traditions of the nation, passed down from generation to generation. Learning a language is not just learning words and grammar, but more importantly, learning the cultural information contained in the language. Language is a vital part of interpersonal communication, as the main tool for communication between people, language can more fully and in detail show the real development of human society. At the same time, there is a certain internal connection between language and culture, which is expressed in the fact that language itself is one of the important carriers of culture, and culture can also realize the value of language. Language is inseparable from the support of culture and can support the inheritance of culture. Translation is a tool of cultural communication, which acts as a bridge and link between the source culture and the

target culture. Translation is a kind of linguistic behavior and cultural communicative behavior, it contains two aspects, languages and cultures, which are inseparable. Translation is a tool of cultural transmission, which acts as a bridge and a link between countries, between the culture of the source language and the culture of the target language. Translation is not just the transition of a text from one language to another, but also the process of harmonization between texts and cultures. It is not only about the transformation of signs, skills or methods of conveying meaning, but also about a very creative and complex. Translation as a practical activity includes both a subject and an object. Translation is an intercultural communicative behavior in which a translator tries to convey information transmitted in one language in another language. Translation, as a practice of human communication, has gone through a long period of development from an initial skill to an independent discipline. As an inevitable means of human communication, translation is a transformation between two languages on the surface, but in essence, translation conveys cultural information. The purpose of translation is to establish an equivalent relationship between the source text and the translated text. In other words, both texts carry the same information. In the course of translation, translators have to overcome various obstacles, one of the main obstacles is intercultural differences. The root of the differences in different language systems lies in cultural differences such as different thinking, life habits, historical heritage and religious beliefs. Cultural differences have a great impact on translation, especially literary works. Proper handling of cultural differences is part of translation skills and is taken seriously. Only by truly understanding the essence of translation, mastering the theory of translation, wisely using translation skills and correctly handling cultural differences can a translator translate literary works perfectly. Nowadays, intercultural communication has become a trend, and the issue of cultural translation is attracting more and more attention. How to preserve the characteristics of one's own national culture and merge with the cultures of different nationalities of the world in interlingual translation is an important issue in each country, and it is worth studying for translators, language students, translators and translation theorists.

2.METHODOLOGY

Language is the carrier of culture. In the process of translating a work from one language to another, the cultural information carried by the culture in the original language also enters into the cultural system of translation. In this process, the existence of cultural differences has created many obstacles to intercultural communication. These problems mainly include two aspects: understanding and expression. In terms of understanding, the cultural information in the original work covers a wide range. As an individual translator, his knowledge is always limited, so it is normal to not understand this or that cultural information in the original text. Due to cultural differences and different customs, people may also be biased towards this or that understanding. If these differences cannot be understood correctly, and there are no relevant reference books to refer to and relevant experts to consult, mistranslations will occur and communication barriers will arise.

One of the key areas of modern scientific activity is the phenomenon of interdisciplinarity, which underlies various modern studies by both domestic and foreign scientists, who are sensitive to such challenges and trends of the new century as hybridity and turbulence. The changing linguistic and geopolitical landscapes of our time require close attention and comprehensive understanding, with the involvement of related sciences, of the cognitive problems of intercultural and interethnic communication, which are inevitably accompanied by linguopsychological and sociocultural risks, the growth of linguistic and regional conflicts. This necessitates the optimization of the most effective techniques and methods of teaching foreign languages religions and cultures. That is why the new generation of translators, to a greater

extent than before, concentrate on achieving mutual understanding in the field of cultures, the effectiveness of cultural dialogue. Many foreign linguists sometimes even hypostatize the importance of culture in translation, calling translators "cultural intermediaries". The concept of culture at the turn of the century acquired a new meaning. If previously the concept of so-called cultural values, works of art, literature, etc. prevailed, then in the modern world the importance of the concept of culture is growing, in which a significant place is given to the description and interpretation of national traditions of people, their way of life, specific behavior, thinking and perception of the surrounding world. In this regard, the priorities of linguistics have also changed: at the current stage of its development, more and more attention is paid to issues related to the national and cultural specificity of languages, with the national originality of the image of the world that has developed in a linguacultural community. Translation scholars, recognizing the special significance that culture has for translation, emphasize the role of translation as the most important means of intercultural communication.

3.FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Culture plays an important role in shaping the beliefs, social habits, customs and traditions of certain groups of people. Language, being an integral part of culture, helps define it. It is a complex system of communication that people adapt to their cultural characteristics. Translation is a process that allows people speaking different languages to understand each other and connect cultures by eliminating cultural barriers. Translation is important for language and culture because it helps improve communication and helps bridge the gap created by different languages. The need for trade and other forms of interdependence between people has given translation great importance. What makes a good translation and how does it affect cultural exchanges. Good translations evoke the same feelings in the native language readers of the translation as in the people reading the original text. A good translation will allow a brand to convey ideas and beliefs in the correct cultural and native language of its audience so that people from different cultures and geographic regions experience the same emotions towards the brand and the product. Culture is not just a set of norms, behavioral attitudes and values that exist in the culture of the speakers of the target language. Culture, among other things, is also an integral condition for the existence of language, the context in which language operates and manifests itself. In other words, language is inextricably linked with culture, with the reality in which people live and with the activities they perform, that is, it is the most important culture-forming element. The spiritual culture of a people is expressed in language, and the system and norm of language influence this culture. The use of language acquires its meaning only in activity. Thus, speaking a certain language is part of the activity within the boundaries of a certain culture. Since both national language and national culture are manifestations of a special national mentality, overcoming only the language barrier in translation is not enough. Understanding the meaning of the cultural barrier and neutralizing it in translation is no less a difficult problem than neutralizing differences of a purely linguistic nature. The success of a translator as a mediator between two cultures depends on knowledge and understanding of the national culture and cultural experience underlying language, speech acts and written texts; knowledge of the potential of two semiotic systems in terms of their ability to create a national picture of the world; understanding of implicitly expressed meanings shared by all members of a linguacultural community and based on cultural values; the ability to correctly select linguistic means for conveying a message in order to achieve the impact of the translation equivalent to the impact of the original. The most important interpersonal aspect of grammar, which is central to both oral and written speech, is modality. Translators who translate marketing materials,

translate apps, dub videos and films, and translate literature must take a keen interest in the culture of the people for whom the text is intended. They may be asked to “localize” the translated material, i.e. adapt it to cultural nuances. This is easy to understand when studying advertising campaigns that have been literally translated rather than designed to appeal to a local audience. Translation was started so that there would be no gaps in communication between different countries, so that cultural exchange and trade could take place. Translation is an opportunity to enrich and form one's own culture by familiarizing oneself with, understanding and borrowing cultural elements of other ethnic groups in the process of interlingual communication. Such work action consists not only in the help of translation services, but can also help a person to improve himself. As Eugene Nida, a famous American researcher of translation, said, translation reproduces one language so that it closely resembles the original language in terms of style and meaning. Translation should help the reader establish a connection with the text and achieve a deep understanding of it in his native language. A translator's knowledge of another culture greatly simplifies translation and also helps ensure the accuracy of the translation. The goal of translation is to achieve semantic equivalence, which can only be achieved if the translator has a good knowledge and understanding of the cultural background of the source and target languages. A cultural universal or human universal is an element, pattern, trait or institution that is common to all humans. It helps us improve communication and is impossible without translation. The exchange of ideas, intercultural growth and trade are the result of the concept of cultural universals, which influences much of our lives. Translation is greatly affected by cultural differences, so the accuracy of the translation of a text is proportional to the translator's knowledge of another culture. Therefore, when translating, not only the translator's linguistic abilities are tested, but also how well he knows the cultural background of the target language. The more the translator knows, the more useful the translation is for an international audience. Therefore, our translators always translate into their native language. Translations can be:

- direct - creative meetings, readings, online conferences;
- indirect.

Translation plays a leading role in overcoming cultural barriers. Specific differences that reach back centuries, spiritual culture cannot be perceived equally and only an approximate idea of the personality of a foreign culture is possible. To become an expert in a foreign culture, you need to live in the corresponding environment for some time and observe all the customs and traditions of another people. Everything can be translated: socio-political and official business documents, scientific and technical texts, newspaper and information materials, as well as fiction. However, the question arises of how well the translation was done. In order to successfully translate a work of fiction, it is necessary to study the writing style and try to reproduce it. We have all repeatedly been indignant that the translation of the book we read differs significantly from the original. In fact, in order to evaluate the translation of a work of fiction, we often resort to subjectivity and do not understand the full scale of the work on the translation. In order to perfectly translate a work, you need to understand how they speak in the original language and translate the essence with the help of appropriate comparisons or phraseological units in the language in which the translation is carried out. In other words, the translator must not only know both languages perfectly, but also understand the meanings of traditional expressions. Translation of documents, of course, seemed to be standard forms of expressions tai everything, but in fact - it is a business style of speech with its own

characteristics in each country. If you turn to oral translation, this is an even more difficult process. Just think that the translator must have not only perfect grammar and a huge set of words of the corresponding language, but also be able to pronounce everything correctly, know all the features of pronunciation of certain sounds and letters. To achieve a positive translation, you should constantly replenish your knowledge, apply it in practice, expand your horizons and speak the language fluently. Translation helps people understand another culture, so the translator's job is to integrate cultural aspects into the translated content. There are many discussions about whether language is part of culture. It is important to understand that culture and language are interconnected. Culture influences various things: literacy, art, dialect and speech, religion, ideology. One form of translation is localization, where the translator must take into account cultural differences, both significant and minor. Even neighboring countries with a common history and similar mentality are home to people with cultural differences. In summary, a translator should take into account even the most minor cultural differences between different social groups. And it is important to understand whether this is an individual feature or a cultural norm in a certain area. Interpreters should also study cultural differences in order to find a common language with people with different backgrounds. Without a translator, it is also impossible to enter the international market. In order to convey a commercial offer to an international audience, it is not enough to simply transform the content from the original to the target language. This is a more complex process. When localizing content, you must ensure that the original message will not offend the feelings of the foreign audience and will not become a reason for ridicule. In essence, the main function of localization is transformation. First, information about local customs and culture is collected, then this knowledge is used to adapt the translated content to the new audience. Incorrectly adapted information can destroy your marketing strategy, and the company will not attract new consumers. To promote a product or service on the international market, the advertising message must be fully understood by the audience. It should not be offensive or offensive, so as not to distract from the product. Localization of content is not only translated and adapted text, it is also the proper use of other elements: images, colors, videos, in some cases, font types. For example, if a company plans to enter the market of countries where sexual minorities do not have rights, gender equality is not recognized by society, and clothing is paid attention to from the point of view of religious meaning, as in Muslim countries, the appearance of models on advertising posters and banners should be reviewed. Cultural differences make every country unique. Each region's culture has evolved over thousands of years, meaning local customs, traditions, and beliefs are deeply ingrained in people. And these differences make global translation difficult. Let's find out why we should pay so much attention to cultural differences:

- self-respect

For example, in the United States, it is perfectly acceptable to make a good-natured joke about someone, to make witty jokes. But such a philosophy is absolutely unacceptable in those countries where the highest human value is reputation, personal dignity, and respect depending on one's position in society, family, or work. This applies to Asian countries, in particular, China, Malaysia, or Indonesia. At the same time, in China or South Korea, Confucian values such as a sense of duty, loyalty, and humility are respected. And in other Asian cultures, entrepreneurship and proactivity are respected.

- family values.

Different cultures have different understandings of what a family is, and considerations may also differ in this matter. For example, in Asian countries, family is understood as relatives — a group of people who are related by blood or in a heterosexual marriage. In other countries where same-sex marriage is legal, a family may mean a same-sex couple raising an adopted child. As you can see, different parts of the world have different understandings of family.

- color in different cultures.

Color as a visual attribute is also a feature of a local culture. Let's take red, for example. In China, it is a symbol of happiness. The English usually associate this color with love and danger. In Japan, it is a symbol of power, vitality, and energy. In Egypt, it is associated with luck. In Iran, it is a symbol of courage. In India, red symbolizes sensuality, spirituality, and purity. But red means death for some African countries. In Nigeria, it is a sign of aggression. Green in many Western cultures symbolizes vitality, nature, and health. In some eastern countries, green also symbolizes new life and fertility. But in Great Britain, green is the color of jealousy, and in China, of godlessness. In Indonesia, green is... forbidden. For many countries, it is a shade of war (olive). As you can see, in different parts of the world, the same things are perceived by people in a positive, neutral, or negative context. Marketers should take these mentality features into account so that the company can successfully develop new markets.

English has a rich system of lexical and grammatical means of expressing modality. The word-formation system of language also plays a major role in the creation of the “cultural world”. It appears as a tool for reflecting reality with the help of linguistic signs. Every language has words that name realities, unique concepts, values, types of situations that are inherent only to a given culture and, accordingly, language. There are several possibilities when translating realities. The language either borrows the name of the concept, or does without it, or invents its own name. Thanks to the intensification of cultural exchange, many realities cease to be a national feature, and one culture penetrates another. The greatest difficulty in translation, however, is not caused by linguistic differences, but by those elements of culture that are above the level of elementary linguistic communication. They represent an extralinguistic reality, connected not with external manifestations of culture (language, gestures, behavior, morals, customs, artifacts), but with internal ones (ideas, beliefs, values). And here the attention of translators is focused to a greater extent not on what can be seen, heard, read or felt, but on what is implied in the message, how it is transmitted, and how it is perceived. The most difficult thing in translation is the correct interpretation of cultural values, cultural stereotypes and norms embedded in the text. What is considered positive in one culture may be negatively interpreted in another. Often, cultural information that does not meet the expectations of the readers of the translated text or concerns some taboo topic may be omitted. Culture can be manifested in the text as an object of description or mention (cultural and historical events, customs, traditions, etc.). In this case, a certain set of background (extralinguistic) knowledge is necessary for the correct interpretation and translation of the text. There were no equivalent words to describe these once foreign objects, so the words came along with the objects. Each of these words can be easily associated with a country. We define a culture by the objects associated with it. Words develop in a language to describe habits, objects, and beliefs unique to a culture, and so they may not have an exact translation into another language.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Many people learn another language at one time or another. In most cases, they do so without the cultural immersion of native speakers. The extent to which the connection between language and culture is appreciated depends on the reasons for learning the language. A person who is interested in becoming fluent in another language because he or she wants to travel, live, work, or study in a country where that language is spoken will soon encounter the language of a particular culture that he or she will want to become familiar with in order to communicate effectively. Language learners often find slang and idiomatic expressions difficult to translate. Language, culture, and translation are inextricably linked. One striking example of this connection is the unique vocabulary and phraseology used by cultures. Many words in a language arise to describe specific objects, beliefs, and behaviors associated with a particular cultural group. The acceptance of the language and culture in the original book by the reader depends on how receptive the reader is to the target languages. If the translation matches the expected horizon of the target language reader, it easily resonates in the depth of the reader, thereby stimulating the acceptance of literary translations. In this way, the translator voluntarily translates the language and culture contained in the literature to match the cognitive level and aesthetics of the target language readers, a process called cultural adaptation. It is an undeniable fact that translation and culture have a deep connection. Good translation can be done by human translators who strengthen the connection between cultures by producing translations that are not only accurate but also take into account the cultural differences that exist between speakers of different languages. Translators introduce target audiences to translations that are intertwined with their culture. Thus, the solution of translation problems related to linguacultural translation is determined by the art of choosing an adequate measure of preserving elements of a foreign-language culture in translation and an acceptable measure of replacing them with functionally similar elements of one's own culture. If this measure is not observed, serious cultural errors are encountered in translations, preventing readers from adequately perceiving the text of the translation. As in any other professional service, there are different levels of product quality, customer service, and reliability in translation. A human translator is still the fastest and most cost-effective way to get a high-quality translation that can evoke the desired emotional response. To sum up the above, we note that translators must combine knowledge of the language itself with knowledge of customs, traditions, morals, and the peculiarities of the national psychology of the speakers of the two cultures, and have background knowledge of national culture and current events known to speakers of the source language.

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